

Retention behaviour of metal ions on plain and tri-*n*-butylamine impregnated titanium(IV) tungstate layers

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Retention behaviour of metal ions has been studied on plain and tri-*n*-butylamine impregnated titanium(IV) tungstate layers. The ion exchange capacity of titanium(IV) tungstate is determined and the selectivity for different metal ions discussed. The mechanism of migration is explained in terms of ion exchange, precipitation and adsorption. Effect of pH of the mobile phase on R_f values of some *d*-block metal ions on both the layers has been studied. Some specific separations have been achieved.

Recently, the reversed phase thin layer chromatography (RPTLC) of metal ions on silica gel-G layers has been studied extensively¹. However, no effort seems to have been made to study the retention behaviour of metal ions on the layers of inorganic ion exchangers using this technique. Among the synthetic inorganic ion exchangers, Ti^{IV} tungstate is known to possess promising thermal and chemical stability². Tri-*n*-butylamine (TBA) being non-polar in nature was used as an impregnating³ material in our earlier study. The present work was undertaken to investigate the RPTLC behaviour of some *d*-block metal ions on titanium(IV) tungstate layers impregnated with TBA.

Titanium(IV) tungstate show high selectivity at low pH and decomposes at high pH, hence solutions of weak acids were chosen as mobile phases in order to prevent the hydrolysis of the exchanger. The complexing acids used as mobile phases are oxalic, citric and tartaric. As a result, some analytically difficult separations were achieved.

Results and Discussion

The chromatographic behaviour of forty metal ions on titanium(IV) tungstate layers has been studied in the following mobile phases : M₁, 0.1 M oxalic acid; M₂, 0.1 M citric acid; M₃, 0.1 M tartaric acid; M₄, 0.1 M oxalic acid + 0.1 M sodium oxalate (1 : 1, v/v); M₅, 0.1 M citric acid + 0.1 M sodium citrate (1 : 1, v/v); M₆, 0.1 M tartaric acid + 0.1 M sodium tartarate (1 : 1, v/v); M₇, 0.1 M HNO₃; M₈, 0.1 M HCl; M₉, 0.1 ammonium oxalate; M₁₀, 0.1 M sodium oxalate; M₁₁, 0.1 M oxalic acid + 0.1 M sodium oxalate + 0.1 M ammonium oxalate (1 : 1 : 1, v/v). The pH of the mobile phases M₁, M₉, M₁₀ and M₁₁ are 1.5, 6.40, 7.59 and 3.55, respectively. The R_f values of metal ions are summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

The interesting feature of this study is a significant difference in the R_f values of chemically similar elements leading to fantastic separation possibilities. Some of the important ones actually achieved are as follows : (a) Tl^I or Ag^I

or Hg₂^{II} - Cu^{II} or Pd^{II} or Cd^{II} or Hg^{II} or Ni^{II} or Co^{II}, UO₂^{II} - Fe^{III} or VO^{II} or Th^{IV} and Ce^{III} - Ce^{IV} in 0.1 M oxalic acid, (b) Cr^{III} - Zn^{II} or Al^{III} or Mn^{II}, Ba^{II} or Sr^{II} - Ca^{II} and Se^{IV} - Pt^{IV} in 0.1 M citric acid and (c) Ag^I or Bi^{III} or Hg₂^{II} or Sb^{III} - Pd^{II} or Cd^{II} or Hg^{II} in 0.1 M tartaric acid. These separation possibilities arise from two effects : (i) the acids chosen as mobile phases form complexes with most of the metal ions, and (ii) Ti^{IV} tungstate layers selectively adsorb certain metal ions.

Table 1. R_f values of metal ions on titanium(IV) tungstate layers

Metal ions	Mobile phase							
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	M ₇	M ₈
Ag ^I	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Pb ^{II}	0.15	0.05	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.15
Cu ^{II}	0.40	0.15	0.60	0.10	0.50	0.55	0.60	0.40
Sb ^{II}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Bi ^{III}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.72
Pd ^{II}	0.30	0.60	0.50	0.28	0.25	0.33	0.60	0.40
Cd ^{II}	0.40	0.70	0.50	0.40	0.20	0.35	0.60	0.45
Hg ^{II}	0.50	0.55	0.60	0.20	0.60	0.65	0.65	0.60
Hg ₂ ^{II}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sn ^{II}	N.D.	0.05	0.10	0.05	0.60	0.00	0.00	N.D.
Tl ^I	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Fe ^{III}	0.30	0.00	0.25	0.05	0.05	0.12	0.75	0.65
VO ^{II}	0.20	0.10	0.00	0.10	0.05	0.20	0.45	0.80
UO ₂ ^{II}	0.70	0.05	0.10	0.35	0.40	0.45	0.70	0.15
Fe ^{II}	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.15	0.23	0.42	0.80
Zn ^{II}	0.45	0.30	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.70
Cr ^{III}	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.25	0.00	0.30	0.48	0.65
Mn ^{II}	0.50	0.30	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.75
Ca ^{II}	0.25	0.40	0.65	0.45	0.30	0.48	0.50	0.15
Zr ^{IV}	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Th ^{IV}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.00
Ce ^{IV}	0.47	0.30	0.50	0.70	0.47	0.40	0.35	0.00
Ce ^{III}	0.05	0.00	0.07	0.05	0.00	0.15	0.35	0.00
La ^{III}	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.12	0.18	0.20	0.00
Nd ^{III}	0.23	0.04	0.05	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.07
Pr ^{III}	0.15	0.08	0.05	0.10	0.05	0.05	0.35	0.20
Sm ^{III}	0.18	0.13	0.15	0.04	0.09	0.04	0.32	0.15
Al ^{III}	0.40	0.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.42	0.80

Table-1 (contd.)

Ba ^{II}	0.60	0.09	0.45	0.70	0.10	0.40	0.35	0.70
Sr ^{II}	0.60	0.15	0.45	0.75	0.10	0.50	0.50	0.80
K ^I	0.35	0.40	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.50	0.20
Rb ^I	0.40	0.42	0.05	0.40	0.25	0.07	0.62	0.30
Cs ^I	0.25	0.35	0.10	0.33	0.20	0.03	0.66	0.35
Ni ^{II}	0.50	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.40	0.40	0.65	0.62
Co ^{II}	0.60	0.40	0.55	0.30	0.30	0.50	0.60	0.72
MoO ₄ ^{II}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
SeO ₃ ^{II}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Pt ^{IV}	0.05	0.40	0.10	0.00	0.12	0.15	0.60	0.70
Ru ^{III}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	T	0.30
Au ^{III}	0.10	0.20	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.12	0.45	0.00

Table 2. R_f values of *d*-block metal ions on TBA impregnated titanium(IV) tungstate layers

Metal ion	Mobile phase			
	M ₁	M ₉	M ₁₀	M ₁₁
Zr ^{IV}	0.00	0.20	0.25	0.20
Cd ^{II}	0.05	0.30	0.10	0.10
Ru ^{III}	0.00	0.15	0.20	0.10
Fe ^{III}	0.00	0.10	0.18	0.04
Co ^{II}	0.00	0.05	0.10	0.04
Ni ^{II}	0.00	0.00	0.16	0.10
Cu ^{II}	0.00	0.10	0.16	0.04
Ag ^I	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hg ^{II}	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.04
Hg ₂ ^{II}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
VO ^{II}	0.00	0.30	0.10	0.14
Fe ^{II}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
MoO ₄ ^{II}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ce ^{III}	0.05	0.10	0.10	0.04
Mn ^{II}	0.18	0.20	0.20	0.20
Au ^{III}	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Zn ^{II}	0.10	0.26	0.30	0.20
Pd ^{II}	0.05	0.20	0.24	0.00
Pt ^{IV}	0.05	0.10	0.20	0.10

A comparison of R_f values of metal ions in 0.1 M HNO₃, a non-complexing acid, used as a mobile phase on titanium(IV) tungstate layers and on titanium(IV) tungstate impregnated papers⁴, both prepared by using same solutions of titanium(IV) chloride and sodium tungstate, suggests that for almost all metal ions, there is a decrease in the R_f values on thin layers probably due to their higher adsorption. The higher ion-exchange capacity of thin layers in comparison to that of impregnated papers may be the reason for this decrease (the ion exchange capacity of titanium(IV) tungstate is 0.58 and for titanium(IV) tungstate impregnated papers is 0.35). The decrease in R_f is more pronounced in case of Pb^{II}, Sb^{III}, Hg₂^{II}, Fe^{III}, Bi^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Th^{IV}, La^{III}, Nd^{III}, Al^{III} and Sn^{II}. This may be due the fact that titanium(IV) tungstate specifically adsorbs these metal ions resulting in much lower R_f . The only exception being Au^{III} which exists as anionic species and thus show higher R_f on the layers than on impregnated papers.

The plots of R_f versus metal ions in 0.1 M oxalic acid and 0.1 M nitric acid used as mobile phases, reveal that in oxalic acid media, there is an increase in the R_f values of

certain metal ions, such as Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ce^{IV}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Hg^{II}, UO₂^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Th^{IV} and Co^{II} due to the formation of anionic oxalate complexes. Similar explanation may also be given for the increase in R_f values of certain metal ions in 0.1 M tartaric acid and 0.1 M citric acid media as the two acids also form anionic complexes with them (The plots are not given for the sake of brevity).

Ions which have zero R_f values may do so owing to (i) precipitation, (ii) ion exchange and (iii) strong adsorption owing to high charge. In order to simulate conditions on thin layers, sodium tungstate was added to the metal ion solution followed by the mobile phase solution. A number of metal ions precipitated under these conditions (Table 3). For all these metal ions, the zero R_f is due to precipitation mechanism. However, the zero R_f for Pt^{IV} may be due to high charge and for Se^{IV} and Mo^{VI} formation of insoluble titanium selenite and titanium molybdate may be the reason for zero R_f value. Further, very low R_f for Tl^I is probably due to the formation of thallos tungstate which is less soluble than thallos nitrate. Sn^{II} has a very low R_f in complexing acid solutions used as mobile phases due to being more extensively hydrolysed.

Table 3. Precipitation of metal ions on unimpregnated layers in the mobile phase used

Mobile phase	Metal ion + sodium tungstate + mobile phase	
	Metal ions which precipitate	Metal ions which do not precipitate
0.1 M Oxalic acid	Pb ^{II} , Bi ^{III} , Hg ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , UO ₂ ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Zr ^{IV} , Th ^{IV} , Ce ^{III} , La ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Ag ^I , Tl ^I , Ca ^{II}	VO ^{II} , MoO ₄ ^{II} , SeO ₃ ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Ru ^{III}
0.1 M Citric acid	Pb ^{II} , Bi ^{III} , Hg ^{II} , Sn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , UO ₂ ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Ag ^I , Cr ^{III} , Zr ^{IV} , Th ^{IV} , La ^{III}	Tl ^I , VO ^{II} , Ru ^{III} , SeO ₃ ^{II} , MoO ₄ ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Sm ^{III}
0.1 M Tartaric acid	Pb ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Sn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , UO ₂ ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Cr ^{III} , Zr ^{IV} , Th ^{IV} , Ce ^{III} , La ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Ag ^I	Tl ^I , VO ^{II} , Ru ^{III} , Pt ^{IV} , SeO ₃ ^{II} , MoO ₄ ^{II} , Zn ^{II}
0.1 M Oxalic acid + 0.1 M sodium oxalate (1 : 1)	Pb ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Hg ₂ ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Fe ^{II} , Al ^{III} , Ag ^I , Zr ^{IV}	Tl ^I , Zn ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Ru ^{III} , MoO ₄ ^{II} , SeO ₃ ^{II}
0.1 M Tartaric acid + 0.1 M sodium tartarate (1 : 1)	Pb ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Hg ₂ ^{II} , Sn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Fe ^{II} , Al ^{III} , Ag ^I	Tl ^I , Zn ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Ru ^{III} , MoO ₄ ^{II} , SeO ₃ ^{II} , VO ^{II}
0.1 M Citric acid + 0.1 M sodium citrate (1 : 1)	Pb ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Hg ₂ ^{II} , Sn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Ag ^I	Tl ^I , Zn ^{II} , Mn ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Ru ^{III} , MoO ₄ ^{II} , SeO ₃ ^{II}
0.1 M HNO ₃	Sb ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Hg ₂ ^{II} , Sn ^{II} , Zr ^{IV} , MoO ₄ ^{II}	Ag ^I , Tl ^I , SeO ₃ ^{II}
0.1 M HCl	Ag ^I , Sb ^{III} , Hg ₂ ^{II} , Tl ^I , UO ₂ ^{II} , Zr ^{IV} , Th ^{IV} , Ce ^{III} , La ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , MoO ₄ ^{II}	SeO ₃ ^{II}

For citric acid media, the plots of R_f versus pK_1 of metal citrate complexes⁵ are quite interesting. For metal ions such as Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Fe^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ca^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cd^{II}, the R_f increases with increase in pK_1 of their citrate complexes.

Fig. 1. Plots of R_f vs pH on plain and TBA impregnated titanium(IV) tungstate layers (x) titanium(IV) tungstate layers, (●) TBA impregnated titanium(IV) tungstate layers

This can be explained on the basis that when pk_1 increases the dissociation of metal citrate complexes decreases thereby causing higher R_f . However, in case of Pb^{II} , UO_2^{II} and Cu^{II} , lower R_f is observed in spite of higher pk_1 values of their citrate complexes. For Pb^{II} and UO_2^{II} , it is probably due to the formation of insoluble citrate complexes whereas for Cu^{II} higher adsorption of Cu-citrate complex on thin layers may be the reason for this behaviour.

The plot of R_f versus metal ions in the mobile phases M_1 and M_4 shows that for some metal ions, the R_f values in the two media differed greatly and the values are much higher in 0.1 M oxalic acid probably due to complexation in strongly acidic media only. However, the values have relatively smaller difference for majority of metal ions due to the formation of oxalate complexes more frequently in a wider pH range. Similar explanation may be given for the plots of R_f versus metal ions in mobile phases M_2 , M_5 and M_3 , M_6 .

It has been observed that the R_f values of metal ions on titanium(IV) based exchangers are inversely proportional to their distribution coefficients (K_d)². This behaviour is expected because when K_d is higher, the metal ion is more strongly held by the ion exchanger and moves less easily. On titanium(IV) tungstate also, this trend was confirmed by determining the R_f of some common metal ions on titanium(IV) tungstate layers in demineralised water used as the mobile phase. The K_d values of these metal ions in demineralised water are already reported² which shows that for these metal ions the sequence of K_d values is the same as the one predicted from R_f : $K_d \rightarrow Hg^{II} > Ba^{II} = Cd^{II} > Zn^{II} = Mn^{II} > Mg^{II} > Al^{III}$, $R_f \rightarrow Hg^{II} < Cd^{II} = Ba^{II} < Zn^{II} = Mn^{II} < Mg^{II} < Al^{III}$. The same is not, however, true for all the metal ions studied. It is considered that the elution sequence can be predicted from K_d values. It follows that the R_f values are not reliable for such prediction because (a) in TLC ascent of mobile phase is too fast for equilibrium to be established, and (b) some of the metal ions interact in different manner on thin layers than on columns

In the RPTLC of metal ions on TBA impregnated layers, the spots are well-defined and no tailing is observed. The R_f values were found to be reproducible and the variation does not exceed 5% of the average value. The impregnated layers are quite stable and firm and are capable of withstanding the mobile phase and chemical operations. For metal ion chromatography, 20% TBA was used for impregnation on the basis of our earlier experience³.

It is interesting to study the effect of pH of the mobile phase on the R_f values of some *d*-block metal ions on plain and TBA impregnated titanium(IV) tungstate layers. For this purpose, plots of R_f versus pH on both the layers were drawn (Fig. 1). A perusal of these plots leads to the following conclusions.

The chromatographic behaviour of these metal ions on impregnated layers shows that for almost all metal ions, the R_f values on impregnated layers are lower than on impregnated ones. This is probably due to the non-polar nature of TBA. The R_f values for a number of metal ions except Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} increase with increase in pH. For Mn^{II} and Cr^{III}, the R_f is almost constant over the entire pH range. In case of VO^{II} and Cd^{II}, the R_f increases till the pH 6.4. On further increase in pH, the R_f suddenly falls and becomes almost zero at pH 7.59. Further, MoO₄²⁻, Hg₂^{II}, Au^{III}, Fe^{II}, Hg^{II} and Ag^I give zero or very low R_f values at all pH. For Hg₂^{II}, Fe^{II}, Ag^I and Au^{III}, this is due to precipitation (Table 4) while zero or very low R_f for Hg^{II} and MoO₄²⁻ may be due to some specific interaction of these ions with the exchange. However, on unimpregnated layers, metal ions such as Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pd^{II}, Fe^{II} and VO^{II} have almost same R_f values over the entire pH range, which may be due to the formation of metal complexes at all pH resulting in higher R_f . The R_f values for Zn^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} are almost constant till the pH value becomes 6.4. On further increases in pH it falls suddenly and becomes almost zero. For Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} this may be due to precipitation in alkaline media but for Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} some specific interaction with the stationary phase may be the reason for this behaviour.

Table 4. Precipitation of metal ions on impregnated layers in the mobile phase used

Mobile phase	Metal ion + sodium tungstate + mobile phase + 20% TBA	
	Metal ions which precipitate	Metal ions which do not precipitate
0.1 M Oxalic acid oxalate	Zr ^{IV} , Ru ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Co ^{II} , VO ^{II} , Cr ^{III} , Au ^{III} , Hg ₂ ^{II} , Pd ^{II} , Pt ^{IV} , Ni ^{II} , Ag ^I , Cd ^{II} , Fe ^{III}	Hg ^{II} , MoO ₄ ^{II}
0.1 M Sodium	Hg ₂ ^{II} , Fe ^{II} , Ag ^I , Au ^{III}	Hg ^{II} , MoO ₄ ^{II}
0.1 M Ammonium oxalate	Ag ^I , Au ^{III} , Hg ^{II} , Fe ^{II}	Hg ^{II} , MoO ₄ ^{II}
0.1 M Oxalic acid + 0.1 M sodium oxalate + 0.1 M ammonium oxalate (1 : 1 : 1, v/v)	Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Cr ^{III}	Hg ^{II} , MoO ₄ ^{II}

Experimental

Thin layer chromatography applicator (Toshniwal) was used to prepare the layers on glass plates (20 × 3 cm). The plates were developed in glass jars (20 × 6 cm).

Titanium(IV) chloride (Reidel) was used. All other chemicals and solvents used were of AnalaR grade.

Test solutions containing 0.1 M chlorides, nitrates or sulfates of metal ions were prepared in a small amount of the corresponding acids⁴. Conventional spot test reagents were used for detection purpose.

Preparation of thin layers : Titanium(IV) tungstate was prepared by mixing 0.30 M solution of titanium(IV) chloride and sodium tungstate in the volume ratio of 1 : 1 at pH 2 and digesting the resulting precipitate at room temperature for 24 h. After filtering and drying, the precipitate was cracked in demineralised water and then placed in 2 M HNO₃ to convert it to the H⁺-form. It was finally washed with demineralised water and the slurry was made by grinding. The slurry was then spread over the glass plates to give 0.1 mm thick layers, then dried at room temperature. For RPTLC, the thin layers were then impregnated with 20% mixture of tri-*n*-butylamine in diethyl ether. Diethyl ether was evaporated by heating the plates at 40 ± 5° for 1 h. The plates were stored in dessicator at room temperature and used as such for chromatography.

Ion exchange capacity : The ion exchange capacity of titanium(IV) tungstate impregnated papers was 0.35 meq/g as reported earlier⁴. For titanium(IV) tungstate prepared as above, it is 0.58 meq/g as determined by column experiments (saturation method).

Procedure : Metal ion solutions (1–2 drops) were spotted on the plates which were developed in the chosen mobile phase by ascending technique. The ascent of the mobile phase was fixed at 11 cm in all cases. After development, the plates were dried and the metal ion spots were detected using appropriate reagent.

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